

Determination of lactic acid-producing bacteria in commercially produced (cooked) and handmade (uncooked) fermented shrimp paste in Zapote, Cavite

Karl B. Buenaobra, Mark Kirby D. Baladiang, Christine J. Erfe, Feneena Marie Czenine L. Ona, Jamaica M. Taurac

Abstract

Lactic Acid Bacteria (LAB) in fermented foods is commonly associated with probiotic properties. The study determined the level of lactic acid-producing bacteria in commercially produced (cooked) and handmade (uncooked) fermented shrimp paste in Zapote, Cavite, which was conducted at Research Laboratory and Department of Medical Laboratory Science in St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor City, Cavite from February 2019 to February 2020. Data analysis and manuscript editing was conducted in respective houses of the researchers from March 2020 to July 2020. Procedure that requires Biosafety Level II like bacterial isolation was done at Bacteriology Section. The handmade (uncooked) fermented shrimp paste (bagoong alamang) utilized in the study was procured from a local market in Zapote, Cavite. Meanwhile, the commercially produced (cooked) fermented shrimp paste utilized in the study was procured from a supermarket in Zapote, Cavite. The determination of lactic acid bacteria in the fermented shrimp paste samples was completed through the evaluation of the isolated lactic acid bacteria using biochemical test and colony counter. The lactic acid bacteria was tested for its gram stain, isolated using MRS agar, 0.9% sodium chloride (NaCl) for dilution, pour plate method of isolation, and incubation at 37°C for 72 hours. Obtained results showed that in three (3) commercially produced (cooked) fermented shrimp paste, sample 1 has the lowest Colony Forming Units (CFUs), and sample 3 has the highest CFUs. Meanwhile, handmade (uncooked) fermented shrimp paste is the highest among all four (4) samples. Generally, the obtained data concludes that in terms of lactic acid bacteria count, handmade (uncooked) fermented shrimp paste is significantly higher than commercially produced (cooked) fermented shrimp paste. Therefore, handmade (uncooked) fermented shrimp paste will provide the maximum quantity of a live probiotic bacteria in a fermented shrimp paste.

Keywords: Lactic acid producing bacteria; Commercially produced (cooked) fermented shrimp paste; Handmade (uncooked) fermented shrimp paste; Zapote, Cavite.

Karl B. Buenaobra*

Mark Kirby D. Baladiang

Christine J. Erfe

Feneena Marie Czenine L. Ona

Jamaica M. Taurac

Medical Laboratory Science Department, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines

***Corresponding author**

To cite this article:

Buenaobra, K. B., Baladiang, M. K. D., Erfe, C. J., Ona, F. M. C. L., & Taurac, J. M. (2022). Determination of lactic acid-producing bacteria in commercially produced (cooked) and handmade (uncooked) fermented shrimp paste in Zapote, Cavite. *SDCA Student Research Journal*, 11(1), 17-21.

Introduction

The Philippine archipelago is a diverse island covered by a vast range of sea and blessed by huge numbers of seafoods. Filipino cuisine is no exception, mixed by different culture throughout the time. Fermented food is part of a Filipino cuisine. Fermented shrimp paste also known as bagoong alamang is a popular condiment that is made from fermented shrimp and salt. Many communities have appreciated fermented foods for its medicinal and health effects throughout history (Behera et al., 2018). Bagoong is typically used as a flavoring or ingredient in many traditional cuisines and can be consumed raw or cooked. Bagoong is frequently the primary source of protein in rural areas, especially those around the coast, where it is typically eaten with vegetables.

Microorganisms are commonly found in fermenting food such as Lactic Acid Bacteria (LAB). Martín et al. (2013) stated that *Lactobacillus* is perhaps the most predominant genus. This organism delivers health benefits and improves shelf life and safety of products, including prevention of pathogenic contamination (Van Boekel et al., 2010).

According to Mikelsaar and Mihkel (2009) and Park et al. (2005), probiotics have been considered safe. Probiotics are widely available, easy to cultivate, and have been studied for their potential impact on health. It has been considered beneficial, indicating its value for additional research and implementation.

Probiotics have also been proven to lessen metabolic problems and increase feed digestion. Probiotic bacteria may produce antimicrobial metabolites, neutralize dietary carcinogens, defuse enteric pathogens through competitive exclusion, modulate mucosal and systemic immune function, neutralize dietary carcinogens, and more. The exact mechanisms by which probiotic bacteria exert their health benefits are not fully understood (Keter et al., 2022; Zielińska & Kolożyn-Krajewska, 2018). However, due to malnutrition, misuse of antibiotics, antibiotic associated diseases, stress, and lifestyle which leads to decrease in normal gut flora, an interest in probiotic treatments has increased.

According to Goldenberg et al., (2017), probiotics are live microbial formulations that, when given in sufficient amounts, may help the host's health. As stated by Robinson and Samona (1992), maintaining the desired balance and a dynamic equilibrium between bacterial communities inside the gut flora is an ongoing struggle. Therefore, the amount of probiotics present plays a huge factor in delivering health benefit. In order to maintain the adequate amount of LAB in our gut, adequate administration is required, therefore; the number of bacteria present in fermented shrimp paste should be counted, this process can be accomplished by colony counting. This is computed through estimation of microbial numbers by Colony Forming Unit (CFU).

A great interest in probiotics is significantly increasing and will certainly expand more in the coming generations. Therefore, this study will substantially improve the living conditions of poor people, and the information regarding the probiotics in fermented shrimp pastes in our country.

Statement of the Problem

The researchers aimed to measure the probiotic lactic acid bacteria levels in commercially produced and handmade fermented shrimp paste. Specifically, this aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level (CFUs) of isolated lactic acid bacteria in:
 - a. Commercially produced (cooked) fermented shrimp paste?
 - b. Handmade (uncooked) fermented shrimp paste?
2. Which of the three (3) samples of commercially produced (cooked) fermented shrimp paste has the highest amount of lactic acid bacteria?
3. Is there a significant difference between the levels of lactic acid bacteria in commercially produced (cooked) and handmade (uncooked) fermented shrimp paste?

Methodology

Research Design

The study is an experimental research design focusing on the determination of lactic acid producing bacteria in commercially produced fermented shrimp paste (cooked) and handmade fermented shrimp paste (uncooked). The researchers also measured which of the following samples has the highest amount of lactic acid bacteria.

Locale of the Study

The site of sample collection was located at Zapote Market, City of Bacoor, Cavite. The experiment was performed mainly at the microbiology laboratory of St. Dominic College of Asia, located in Emilio Aguinaldo Highway, Bacoor, Cavite, 4102.

Instruments

The instruments needed are as follows; gloves, face masks, laboratory gown, petri dish, pipette, micropipette, Erlenmeyer flasks, measuring cylinder, beaker glass, analytical balance, stirring rod, autoclave, test tubes, test tube rack, centrifugation, glass object, glass cover, microscope, colony counter, oven, refrigerator, incubator, air flow cabinet, hotplate, digital camera, and pencil.

Reagent

The materials used in this study are as follows: Commercially produced and handmade fermented shrimp paste, 70% alcohol, Ethyl alcohol, Kovac reagent, hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂). Analytical grade chemicals used are procured from an authorized stores located at Bambang LRT Station in Metro Manila. Other chemicals are provided by St. Dominic College of Asia.

Procurement of Fermented Shrimp Paste Sample

Samples are purchased from near trusted markets. The samples were immediately transferred in a sealed storage to avoid deterioration.

Preparation of Agar and Fermented Shrimp Paste Sample

Workplace was sterilized with antiseptic (70% ethanol), and aseptic technique was observed by the researchers throughout the experimentation period to avoid risks of contamination.

a) *De Man, Rogosa, and Sharpe Agar (MRS Agar) Preparation*

The process can be done by measuring 70 g of MRS Agar mixed with 1000 mL of distilled water and heated until boiling point to dissolve the medium completely. The heat was turned off when the agar turns into its desired amber color. This task is completed by sterilizing the dissolved agar by autoclave at 121°C for 15 minutes.

b) *Cooked Fermented Shrimp Sample Preparation*

The process can be done by weighing ten grams (10 g) from each three (3) samples of commercially produced (cooked) fermented shrimp paste and placing it in a sterile five-hundred milliliters (500 ml) Erlenmeyer flask separately. This task is completed by adding ninety milliliters (90 ml) of sterile 0.9% NaCl to each sample to achieve a 1:10 dilution.

c) *Uncooked Fermented Shrimp Sample Preparation*

The process can be done by weighing three (3) ten grams (10 g) of handmade (uncooked) fermented shrimp paste and placing it in a three (3) sterile five-hundred milliliters (500 ml) Erlenmeyer flask. This task is completed by adding ninety milliliters (90 ml) of sterile 0.9% NaCl to each sample to achieve a 1:10 dilution.

d) *Preparation of 0.9% NaCl solution.*

This process can be done by preparing four (4) sterile test tubes as saline blanks with nine milliliters (9 ml) of 0.9% NaCl. Covered with foil to cover each of the four (4) test tubes and transferred to an autoclave compatible test tube rack. This task is completed by sterilization technique using autoclave.

Experimentation

a) *Isolation Procedure for Commercially Produced (Cooked) Fermented Shrimp Paste*

This process can be done by suspending ten grams (10g) of commercially produced (cooked) fermented shrimp paste into a 90 ml of sterile 0.9% NaCl to achieve a 1:10 dilution followed by 10-fold serial dilution. A 1 ml sample was taken from each diluted sample and inoculated in MRS agar using micropipette. Molten MRS agar was cooled down to 45°C and was poured over the surface to produce a layer-plate. This task is completed by incubating at thirty-seven degree Celsius (37°C) for seventy-two hours (72 hours).

b) *Isolation Procedure for Handmade (Uncooked) Fermented Shrimp Paste*

This process can be done by suspending ten grams (10g) of handmade (uncooked) prepared fermented shrimp paste into a 90 ml of sterile 0.9% sodium chloride (NaCl) to achieve a 1:10 dilution followed by 10-fold serial dilution. A 1 ml sample was taken from diluted sample and inoculated in MRS agar using micropipette. Molten MRS agar was cooled down to 45°C and was poured over the surface to produce a layer-plate. The agar plate was incubated at thirty-seven degree Celsius (37°C) for seventy-two hours (72 hours).

Biochemical Test

a) Gram Stain

i. Preparation of a slide smear:

This process is accomplished by dropping a normal saline solution (NSS) on the slide and by using inoculating loop to transfer a drop of suspended culture to the microscope slide. Culture is spread with an inoculation loop to an even thin film. Preparation of slide smear is completed by fixation; move the slide circularly over the flame to prevent overheating or forming of ring patterns in the slide.

ii. Gram staining

Crystal violet stain is added over the fixed culture. After 10 to 60 seconds, the stain is poured off, and the excess stain is rinsed with water. Iodine solution is used to cover the smear for 10 to 60 seconds. Iodine solution is poured off, and the slide is rinsed with running water. Excess water from the surface is shaken off. A few drops of decolorizer is added to the slide. The slide is rinsed with water in five (5) seconds. To prevent excess decolorization in the gram-positive cells, stop adding decolorizer as soon as the solvent is not colored as it flows over the slide. This test is completed by counterstaining with basic fuchsin solution for 40 to 60 seconds. The fuchsin solution is washed off with water. The slide was air-dried after shaking off excess water.

b) Colony Count

This process was done by counting each (both large and small) colony carefully (using magnifying colony counter if needed). Each colony represents a "colony forming unit" (CFU). The number of microorganisms present in the test sample is determined using the formula: $CFU/mL = CFU \times \text{dilution factor} \times 1/\text{aliquot}$ for accurate counts. This process is completed by computing the CFU/mL by following the formula.

Statistical Treatment

Statistical analysis was carried out by the use of independent T-test. In order to ascertain whether there is statistical evidence that the related population means are significantly different, it compares the means of two independent groups. P values less than 0.05 will be considered significant.

Food and Nutrition Research Institute (FNRI)

Samples were sent to FNRI on the day of sample procurement to confirm the presence of lactic acid bacteria in our sample.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Lactic acid bacteria counted in commercially produced (cooked) fermented shrimp paste

Fermented Shrimp Sample	Sample	Lactic Acid Bacteria Count (CFUs)
Commercially produced (cooked) fermented shrimp paste	1	3 CFU/mL
	2	4 CFU/mL
	3	6 CFU/mL

Table 1 shows the counted LAB in the three (3) samples of commercially produced (cooked) fermented shrimp paste. After counting the colonies of the three (3) samples of commercially produced (cooked) fermented shrimp paste, the CFUs were computed.

It can be observed that among the three (3) samples of commercially produced (cooked) fermented shrimp pastes, sample 3 yields the highest count of LAB, whereas sample 1 yields the lowest count of LAB.

Table 2. Lactic acid bacteria counted in handmade (uncooked) fermented shrimp paste

Fermented Shrimp Sample	Sample	Lactic Acid Bacteria Count (CFUs)
Handmade (uncooked) fermented shrimp	1	108,000 or 10.8×10^4 CFU/mL
	2	119,000 or 11.9×10^4 CFU/mL
	3	124,000 or 12.4×10^4 CFU/mL

Table 2 shows the counted LAB in the one (1) sample of handmade (uncooked) fermented shrimp paste. After counting the colonies of the three (3) trials of handmade (uncooked) fermented shrimp pastes, the CFUs were computed. Among the three (3) trials of handmade (uncooked) fermented shrimp paste, trial 3 yields the highest count of LAB, whereas trial 1 yields the lowest count of lactic acid bacteria.

Table 3. Test for significant difference between the presence of lactic acid bacteria

Group	Average	P-value	Significance	Ho Decision
Cooked fermented shrimp	4.33	0.001	Significant	Reject
Uncooked fermented shrimp	117000			

*Significant at .05 alpha level

Table 3 shows that there is a significant difference between the presence of LAB in handmade (uncooked) and commercially produced (cooked) fermented shrimp paste. The computed p-value is 0.001 which is less than .05 alpha level. Therefore, there is a significant difference and null hypothesis is rejected. Hence in terms of lactic count, handmade (uncooked) fermented shrimp paste is significantly higher than commercially produced (cooked) Fermented shrimp paste.

Table 4. FNRI test results for lactic acid bacterial count in fermented shrimp paste

Cooked	Uncooked
<10	190,000

Table 4 shows that the result of fermented shrimp paste samples tested in FNRI supports the claim that there are more lactic acid bacteria present in handmade (uncooked) than the commercially produced (cooked) fermented shrimp paste. The live probiotics in commercially produced (cooked) fermented shrimp paste was lower compared to the handmade (uncooked) fermented shrimp. However, this does not mean that the commercially produced (cooked) fermented shrimp paste contains less health risk, and less health benefits because it contains lower live probiotics than the handmade (uncooked) fermented shrimp paste. As argued by Adams (2010) cited in the study of Nakagawa et al. (2016) most of the effects of probiotics that are produced by their living cells are also produced by populations of their dead cells.

Meanwhile, the live probiotics in handmade (uncooked) fermented shrimp paste was higher compared to the commercially (cooked) produced fermented shrimp paste. However, this does not mean that the handmade (uncooked) fermented shrimp paste contains more health risk, and more health benefit because it contains more live probiotics than commercially (cooked) produced fermented shrimp paste. Consuming either commercially produced (cooked) fermented shrimp paste or handmade (uncooked) fermented shrimp will be both beneficial. In order to create and sustain a healthy microbiota, you should give your gut a diversity of beneficial bacteria, so that the results of this study will be a great candidate for that (Bentley, 2017). The potential for the next-generation probiotics is real, and their development should be supported by research funding, and this study is just a step towards a greater discovery about our fermented shrimp paste in the Philippines.

Conclusions

Through the findings based on the data gathered and experimentation done, the answers to the objectives can be drawn with credible and valid points. Therefore, the researchers conclude that:

1. The data shows that the lactic acid bacteria of both commercially (cooked) produced and handmade (uncooked) fermented shrimp paste were isolated. The lactic acid bacteria in commercially produced (cooked) fermented shrimp paste was determined to be statistically the lowest. Meanwhile, the lactic acid bacteria in handmade (uncooked) fermented shrimp paste was statistically the highest.
2. The lactic acid bacteria in handmade (uncooked) fermented shrimp paste was determined to be statistically the highest compared to all other samples.
3. Among the three (3) samples of commercially produced (cooked) fermented shrimp paste, sample 1 has the highest amount of lactic acid bacteria.
4. Lactic acid bacteria of handmade (uncooked) fermented shrimp paste is significantly higher than commercially produced (cooked) fermented shrimp paste.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion made in the study, the following are the recommendations of the researchers:

1. Future researchers may identify and list all the lactic acid bacteria that can be found in fermented shrimp paste in Cavite.
2. Future researchers may identify if the lactic acid bacteria found in fermented shrimp paste in Cavite are Probiotic bacteria.
3. Future researchers may identify the different strain of lactic acid bacteria that can be found in fermented shrimp paste in Cavite.
4. Future researchers may perform a thorough understanding of risks and immunological benefits of consuming lactic acid bacteria found in fermented shrimp paste in Cavite.
5. The future researchers may conduct a study on how to maintain the lactic acid bacteria in commercially produced (cooked) fermented shrimp paste at high amount.
6. The researchers may conduct a study regarding the inactivation of lactic acid bacteria found in fermented shrimp paste.

7. Future researchers may conduct a study about the effectiveness of the lactic acid bacteria in fermented shrimp paste against another microorganism.
8. Future studies may use a different type of fermented paste in determining the lactic acid levels.
9. Future researchers may develop a mixture of probiotics rich food product to produce a more efficient rich in probiotics food-source.
10. Future researchers may use our data to construct a research-based consumption limitation or dosage.
11. Future researchers may conduct the same study but will utilize an anaerobe culture technique and compare the data for significance.

References

- Adams, C. A. (2010). The probiotic paradox: live and dead cells are biological response modifiers. *Nutrition Research Reviews*, 23 (1), 37-46. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0954422410000090>
- Behera, S. S., Ray, R. C., & Zdolec, N. (2018). Lactobacillus plantarum with functional properties: An approach to increase safety and shelf-life of fermented foods. *BioMed Research International*, 2018, 9361614. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/9361614>
- Bentley, R. (2017, August 29). *L. fermentum – A common probiotic strain*. Humarian. <https://humarian.com/l-fermentum/>
- Goldenberg, J. Z., Yap, C., Lytvyn, L., Lo, C. K. F., Beardsley, J., Mertz, D., & Johnston, B. C. (2017). Probiotics for the prevention of Clostridium difficile-associated diarrhea in adults and children. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, (12), CD006095. <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD006095.pub4>
- Keter, M. T., El Halfawy, N. M., & El-Naggar, M. Y. (2022). Incidence of virulence determinants and antibiotic resistance in lactic acid bacteria isolated from food products. *Future Microbiology*, 17(5), 325-337. <https://doi.org/10.2217/fmb-2021-0053>
- Martín, R., Miquel, S., Ulmer, J., Kechaou, N., Langella, P., & Bermúdez-Humarán, L. G. (2013). Role of commensal and probiotic bacteria in human health: A focus on inflammatory bowel disease. *Microbial Cell Factories*, 12, 71. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1475-2859-12-71>
- Mikelsaar, M., & Zilmer, M. (2009). Lactobacillus fermentum ME-3 – an antimicrobial and antioxidative probiotic. *Microbial Ecology in Health and Disease*, 21(1), 1-27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08910600902815561>
- Nakagawa, H., Shiozaki, T., Kobatake, E., Hosoya, T., Moriya, T., Sakai, F., Taru, H., & Miyazaki, T. (2016). Effects and mechanisms of longevity induced by Lactobacillus gasseri SBT2055 in Caenorhabditis elegans. *Aging Cell*, 15(2), 227-236. <https://doi.org/10.1111/acer.12431>
- Park, J. H., Lee, Y., Moon, E., Seok, S. H., Baek, M. W., Lee, H. Y., Kim, D. J., Kim, C. H., & Park, J. H. (2005). Safety assessment of Lactobacillus fermentum PL9005, a potential probiotic lactic acid bacterium, in mice. *Journal of Microbiology and Biotechnology*, 15(3), 603-608. <https://koreascience.kr/article/JAKO200504704044856.pdf>

- Robinson, R. K., & Samona, A. (1992). Health aspects of 'bifidus' products: A review. *International Journal of Food Sciences and Nutrition*, 43(3), 175-180.
- Van Boekel, M., Fogliano, V., Pellegrini, N., Stanton, C., Scholz, G., Lalljie, S., Somoza, V., Knorr, D., Jasti, P. R., & Eisenbrand, G. (2010). A review on the beneficial aspects of food processing. *Molecular Nutrition & Food Research*, 54(9), 1215-1247.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/mnfr.200900608>
- Zielińska, D., & Kolożyn-Krajewska, D. (2018). Food-origin lactic acid bacteria may exhibit probiotic properties: Review. *BioMed Research International*, 2018, 5063185.
<https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/5063185>